

Conference Abstract

Resilience among laid-off employees in banking sector: *evidence from Lebanon*

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Received: 30 May 2023 | Published: 20 Jun 2023

Citation: Nakhle P (2023) Resilience among laid-off employees in banking sector: *evidence from Lebanon*.

ARPHA Conference Abstracts 6: e107233. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.6.e107233>

Abstract

In light of extensive research examining job termination and its effects on the economy, organizations, and individuals (Anger et al. 2017, Deb et al. 2011, Hanisch 1999, Leana and Feldman 1988), this study aims to specifically explore the impact of fear and resilience on reemployment among laid-off employees from the Lebanese banking sector.

Given the significant challenges faced by the Lebanese banking sector recently, resulting in a substantial number of employee layoffs, it is essential to investigate the extent to which these emotions influence the reemployment outcomes of affected individuals.

To note that this paper is a conceptual paper intended to lay the groundwork for future analysis in the areas of fear and resilience, specifically in the time after job termination in the Lebanese banking sector.

This paper will adopt a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to gather comprehensive data. The sample will consist of former employees who were laid off from various Lebanese banks during one of the most severe economic collapses.

The quantitative phase will involve administering a standardized survey instrument to measure the emotions of fear and resilience experienced by the participants. Fear will be assessed by examining anxiety levels, concerns about financial stability, and worries about career prospects. Resilience will be evaluated by exploring coping mechanisms, self-

efficacy, and adaptability to change. The survey will also include demographic and employment-related questions.

In the qualitative phase, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with a subset of participants to gain a deeper understanding of their experiences. The interviews will explore the specific fears encountered, the strategies employed to cope with the layoff, and the impact of these emotions on the participants' job search process.

The collected data will be analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative techniques. Statistical analyses, such as correlation and regression analyses, will be conducted to examine the relationships between fear, resilience, and reemployment outcomes.

The qualitative data will be analyzed thematically to identify recurring patterns, emerging themes, and narratives related to the research question.

The findings of this research will contribute to the existing literature on the impact of emotions on reemployment following job loss, particularly within the context of the Lebanese banking sector. The results will shed light on the extent to which fear and resilience influence individuals' ability to secure new employment after being laid off. Furthermore, the study will provide valuable insights into the coping mechanisms and strategies that laid-off employees utilize to navigate the challenging job market.

The implications of this research are twofold. First, it will inform policymakers and practitioners about the emotional experiences of laid-off employees in the Lebanese banking sector and highlight the importance of addressing their fears and enhancing their resilience during the transition to reemployment. Second, it will contribute to the development of effective support programs and interventions aimed at facilitating the successful reintegration of laid-off individuals into the workforce.

Overall, this research will deepen our understanding of the emotions of fear and resilience among laid-off employees and their impact on reemployment outcomes. By examining these factors in the specific context of the Lebanese banking sector, it will provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by individuals in a turbulent economic environment and offer recommendations to promote their successful reemployment.

Keywords

fear, resilience, Lebanese banking sector, laid-off employees.

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Presented at

CABMR 2023 colloquium on Resilience and Cybersecurity, held on March 9, 2023, at Ascencia Business School – Collège de Paris, ISF campus, La Défense, Paris, France.

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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